

1. Introduction

Plant transpiration is a biophysical process in which water is absorbed from the roots of plants, passing through the vascular system of roots, stems, branches and leaves, and finally exhausted into the atmosphere as water vapor (*Dingman, 2015*). It is associated with the energy balance of the land surface, determines the hydrological response of the catchment and influences regional and global climate (*Bonan, 2008*). Transpiration accounts for 60-80% of land evapotranspiration, which entails that it is the dominant flux in the global water cycle (*Schlesinger and Jasechko, 2014*). Furthermore, transpiration maintains the survival of plants. When cellular structures in the leaf surface area of plants called stomata open for the control of transpiration, this is accompanied by the exchange of carbon dioxide for photosynthesis (*Damour et al., 2010*), and also contributes some functions such as cooling the plant or changing the osmotic pressure.

To quantify the amount or the rate of transpiration, measuring leaf stomatal conductance or sap flow within the xylem is considered a direct and accessible approach that can then be converted to transpiration. However, instruments for measuring leaf stomatal conductance are non-automatic and non-continuous, which makes it relatively difficult to apply them extensively (*Dugas et al., 1993*). Thereafter, Huber (*1932*) was one of the first users to apply heat as a tracer to determine sap flow, later collectively known as the sap flow method (*Smith and Allen, 1996; Vandegehuchte and Steppe, 2013*). Given the ease of replication and automation of these thermometric sap flow probes, they have been widely used in the study of plant transpiration. Nevertheless, sap flow methods are still expensive and time-consuming.

Compared to sap flow measurements, weather stations are more densely located and have correspondingly complete meteorological monitoring information. If the relationship between sap flow and meteorological data could be properly exploited, an adaptive prediction model covering the lack of sap flow measurement data would be developed. Conceptually, physical or empirical based models require reanalysis of input data and adjustment of their parameters to estimate sap flow in different circumstances (*Tognetti et al., 2005*). The application of these mathematical models is further restricted by the complexity of their parameterization, which demands a deeper understanding of all relevant physical processes between sap flow and environmental variables (*Mencuccini et al., 2019*).

As an alternative to traditional models, machine learning (ML) algorithms have been proposed because they do not require knowledge of internal factors and can provide straightforward solutions for nonlinear functions (*Fan et al., 2021*). In recent years, several studies have been conducted to intend the feasibility of predicting sap flow. For example, Amir et al. (*2021*) proposed different machine learning techniques such as linear regression, support vector regression and decision tree to forecast tomato sap flow. Li et al. (*2022*)

advanced a convolutional neural network-gated recurrent unit method, to capture complex nonlinear dependencies of environmental factors and assessments of sap flow. However, studies using ML to predict sap flow are currently sparse, mainly using specific regional area or from merely single species data as model inputs. A large-scale spatial model of plant sap flow has yet to emerge.

We attempt to fill this gap by developing a sap flow prediction model through open data sources and machine learning. From a comprehensive information perspective, data sharing or open data sources are particularly important. The SAPFLUXNET (*Poyatos et al., 2016*), a global sap flow measurement database, dedicated to compiling global sap flow measurement data. It serves as an opportune source to build our database, which includes hydro-meteorological drivers in addition to time series of sap flow, as well as metadata on the site and stand characteristics, plant attributes, and details of measurement techniques.

As for the choice of ML algorithm, long short-term memory (LSTM) is adopted due to its appropriation to process temporal sequences data (*Karevan and Suykens, 2020; Shi et al., 2015*). Additionally, static characteristics also perform in the input features. In this thesis, there are total of one warm-up and three experiments designed, where different variables are gradually put in each stage, and 6 dynamic and 15 static variables are considered in the ultimate model.

By establishing the LSTM model, sap flow is estimated, offering the possibility of assessing plant transpiration within the design scope, even further in collaboration with other subjects in the future, such as geographic information or plant biology. More importantly, it supplies information on potential changes in the global water cycle that influences rational water resource managements and decision-making projects around the world.

The goal of this master thesis is to train a neural network model – LSTM, to predict sap flow from a European database. The following research questions will be discussed together:

- (1) How strong is the relationship between each environmental factor and sap flow?
- (2) How does the missing data of the sap flow affect the prediction performance of the neural network?
- (3) How important are static variables in the model extension?
- (4) How well does our model extrapolate the state of the system in the presence of extreme values?

2. Machine Learning Algorithm

2.1 Artificial Neural Network

In general, ANNs are trying to simulate as the brain or biological neural networks processing, according to different connections and memory information (*Mishra and Srivastava, 2014*). It

is used by a large number of nodes and each node generates a specific output, based on the activation function (*Norgaard et al., 2000*). In addition, the connection between every two nodes is associated with a bias and a weight, which is equivalent to the memory of the artificial neural network (*Bulsari, 1993*). To sum up, the network itself is usually an approximation of some algorithm in nature, or an expression of a logical strategy.

2.2 Recurrent neural network

Recurrent neural network (RNN) is a class of ANN model in which connections between nodes are able to create a loop, allowing output from some nodes to affect subsequent input to the same nodes. In other words, the typical feature of the RNNs architecture is a cyclic connection, which enables RNNs to update the current state based on the past state and the current input data (*Yu et al., 2019*). This model is introduced to overcome the defect of feed-forward time series network.

In RNNs, the basic network consists of standard recurrent cells combining the recurrent information $h(t)$ with the input, paired with activation functions such as sigmoid or tanh functions. The input thus has a memory to pass previous information to each other and good to process sequences of time. However, this kind of RNNs model is not able to handle long-term dependencies. Due to the growing gap between the related inputs, it is difficult to learn connection information, and false signals that cause flowing backward in time tend to either explode or vanish. Therefore, new RNNs are proposed and differentiated mainly by the recurrent cell and network architecture, which enable RNNs model with different capacities.

2.3 Long Short-Term Memory

In 1997, Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (*1997*) proposed a new node called long short-term memory (LSTM). Its role is to improve the memory capacity of the standard recurrent cell by introducing a “gate” within both input and output. After that, Gers et al. (*2000*) identified a weakness of original LSTM networks that once time series are not a priori segmented into subsequences with well-defined starts and ends, an occasional reset mechanism needs to be established. Therefore, it modified the original model to add a forget gate into the cell, which is the most common LSTM nowadays.

As mentioned, the LSTM model is a powerful RNNs model, which was designed to overcome the vanishing or exploding gradient problem while learning long-term dependencies, even with very long minimal time lags (*Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1996*). The core concept of LSTM architecture is a set of recurrently connected blocks, known as memory blocks. which maintains their state and modulates the flowing non-linear information over time (*Van Houdt et al., 2020*). For this reason, LSTM is one of the most advanced networks for dealing with temporal sequences, and also suitable for any other problem that requires temporal memory.

On the whole, there are three gates and one memory cell state to generate the recurrent information $h(t)$ in LSTM. The gates include the forget gate $f(t)$, the input gate $i(t)$ and the output gate $o(t)$, while the memory cell state $c(t)$ is to store the information. The network is able to interact with the cells only via the gates.

As for training process, an approach called back propagation through time (BPTT) is often used in recurrent networks to calculate an error gradient (Williams and Zipser, 1995), based on the extension of the standard back propagation. BPTT starts by unrolling a recurrent neural network in time. The unrolled network contains several inputs and outputs, but each copy of the network shares the same parameters. Then the gradient of the loss is obtained with respect to all network parameters. That is, during the backward pass, the gradient is accumulated before being back propagated to the current layer.

3. Database and Experiments

3.1 The SAPFLUXNET database

The SAPFLUXNET (Poyatos *et al.*, 2021) is a project with an initiative aiming at compiling a global database of sap flow measurements in plants led by Centre for Research on Ecology and Forestry Applications (CREAF) researchers and an international team of collaborators. The main goal of the SAPFLUXNET is to advance the scientific understanding of the ecological factors underlying plant transpiration worldwide.

The SAPFLUXNET version 0.1.5 database contained 202 globally distributed datasets from 121 geographic locations, especially in Europe, the eastern USA and Australia. To go further, the SAPFLUXNET contains sap flow data for 2714 individual plants (1584 angiosperms and 1130 gymnosperms), belonging to 174 species (141 angiosperms and 33 gymnosperms), 95 different genera, and 45 different families. All species are tree species except one - *Elaeis guineensis*, which is belongs to a palm. As for time scales, the oldest dataset in the SAPFLUXNET was from 1995 and all recorded plants had periods ranging from at least 3 months to 16 years.

3.2 Required database

Although the SAPFLUXNET database was distributed all over the world, the European region accounted for the largest share at 47.5% (96 of 202 globally datasets). The eastern USA and Australia also had higher representation, with 17.8% and 11.9%, respectively. The rest of the datasets were scattered rather widely around the world. For the first attempt at a large scale sap flow prediction model, we selected the European region as a representative dataset.

All datasets of SAPFLUXNET contained temporal patterns of the main hydrometeorological drivers. Here, we considered 6 environmental variables, or regarded as dynamic variables, which were “air temperature” (AT), “relative humidity” (RH), “vapour pressure deficit” (VPD), “shortwave incoming radiation” (SW), “precipitation” (PR) and “wind speed” (WS). Among them, the first three variables were available in all datasets, although vapour pressure deficit was absent in some datasets, it could be calculated by empirical equation. By contrast, parts of datasets were missing the last three variables, and those with missing ones would be excluded. As for the soil water content variable, it was not considered for the time being due to the lack of measurement information from a relatively large number of datasets.

Concerning about the static characteristics, they were divided into three levels in the SAPFLUXNET, which were site, stand and plant variables, from large to small scale. To maximize the available datasets, this static variable was excluded whenever there were more than 10 datasets missing this variable. According to this rule, there were six variables at site-level, namely “latitude”, “longitude”, “elevation”, “annual mean temperature”, “annual mean precipitation” and “vegetation type”. The terrestrial biome classifications, based essentially on annual mean temperature and annual mean precipitation, were excluded. At stand-level, a total of seven variables were selected, “mean stand age”, “canopy height”, “total basal area”, “total stem density”, “aspect”, “slope and/or relief” and “soil texture class”. Last, plant-level referred to each individual tree, and only two variables were available here, “diameter at breast height (DBH)” and “genus name”. Because of the specificity of the genus name, we separated it out, and again, those genera with less than 10 plants were excluded.

In summary, after selecting all 21 variables, including 6 dynamic and 15 static variables, we used 49 eligible European datasets out of 96 databases in Europe for this thesis.

3.3 Experimental design

Overall, we designed a total of four experiments (as **Figure 1**). During the warm-up, one from each of the five different plant genera was selected as a representative model. As for other three experiments, the number of datasets gradually increased from small to large. In other words, a specific location - France, and a representative plant of Europe –*Fagus sylvatica*, were chosen to manipulate the conditions of different experiments. The reason for choosing France was mainly because it was one of the most abundant data regions. In the experiment 1, we only considered the datasets of genus *Fagus* and the French region, with total 20 plants. In the experiment 2, the scale was expanded to the whole of European countries, while the genus remained unchanged, with 83 plants in total. In the experiment 3, data from the remaining four genera were added, that is all 618 species of plants in our database.

As for input features, due to the difference of the area region and plant genus, the certain static variables were added gradually each time. During the warm-up, dynamic variables were the only input features to be considered. In the experiment 1, the plant variable, namely DBH, was the first static variable to be added. In the experiment 2, the site and stand variables were joined at this moment, as well as the plant height used for comparison. In the experiment 3, the genus name variable was included last.

Lastly, to evaluate model performance, the NSE value was the evaluation metric we used. In addition, in all experiments, 10 trials were simulated for each case and their statistics were calculated.

Figure 1 The process of all experiments

4. Results

4.1 Data coverage

Our database contained 49 datasets spread across Europe, from 28 geographical location sites (as **Figure 2**). This included 9 countries: Czech Republic, Germany, France, Netherlands, Portugal, Russian Federation, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom. The easternmost point was the Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Region of Russia and the southwestern point was the Spanish island of Tenerife.

4.2 Results of experiments

In the warm-up, we picked five plant data representing different genera and analyzed the correlation between the sap flow of each plant and environmental factors. After that, we also simulated daily pattern for each plant by LSTM model.

Figure 2 Geographic and biogeographic distribution of the database

Table 1 highlights the results of correlation analysis. The trends from five datasets are overall considerable similar. Among them, the sap flow of three genera is most related to SW, while VPD and RH have the highest correlation with the sap flow of one genus.

To take it a step further, SW has the highest positive correlation with sap flow, ranging from 0.589 to 0.805, with a mean value 0.679. In addition, AT and VPD also have a significant positive correlation with sap flow. The former ranges from 0.466 to 0.680, while the latter ranges from 0.392 to 0.761. RH, on the contrary, reflects a negative correlation with sap flow to about the same extent as the previous two, ranging from -0.785 to -0.480, with average in -0.608. Lastly, PR and WS show relatively low relationship to sap flow, with average in -0.127 and 0.154 respectively. As for Standard deviation, RH and VPD have relatively large variations, with 0.116 and 0.129, while the other variables are relatively constant, with values less than 0.1.

Table 1 Correlation analysis between environmental variables and sap flow

Genus	Environmental variables					
	AT	RH	VPD	SW	PR	WS
<i>Fagus</i>	0.568	-0.609	0.640	0.805	-0.132	0.218
<i>Quercus</i>	0.466	-0.487	0.392	0.668	-0.186	0.072
<i>Pinus</i>	0.680	-0.681	0.761	0.663	-0.118	0.183
<i>Picea</i>	0.481	-0.480	0.566	0.589	-0.042	0.138
<i>Pseudotsuga</i>	0.614	-0.785	0.712	0.671	-0.156	0.158
Mean value	0.562	-0.608	0.614	0.679	-0.127	0.154
SD	0.081	0.116	0.129	0.070	0.048	0.049

In the experiment 1, we used 2 stands, namely “FRA_HES_HE1_NON” and “FRA_HES_HE2_NON”, to generate two groups: “no-pick” and “pick”, containing 20 and 10 plant data separately, and then compared the performance between the two models.

Figure 3 shows the comparison of NSE between two groups in the experiment 1. The median NSE value of the *no-pick* model is 0.788, ranging from 0.724 to 0.845. After selecting data, the median NSE value of the *pick* model decreased to 0.745, and range from 0.692 to 0.923. Although the *pick* model has a better maximum NSE, the median is smaller and more variable than the *no-pick* model. Therefore, in general, the *pick* model does not significantly outperform the *no-pick* model.

Figure 3 The best NSE value and boxplot of the testing period for the experiment 1

In the experiment 2, according to the use of different static variables as input features, it was divided into four groups: “*PL*”, “*ST*”, “*PL+ST*” and “*PL+ST extra*”. We simulated four models and calculated their performance.

Figure 4 shows the NSE values of the 4 groups in the experiment 2. The median NSE value of the *PL* model is 0.694, and ranges from 0.456 to 0.819, indicating the greatest variation. The *ST* model has the overall lowest NSE value, ranging from 0.320 to 0.498, with a median of 0.432. The median NSE value of the *PL+ST* model is 0.788, ranging from 0.693 to 0.856. The *PL+ST extra* model is very similar with the *PL+ST* model, from 0.676 to 0.815. In conclusion, models with plant variables achieved better NSE values.

In the experiment 3, through the threshold limit of the extreme value, it was divided into two groups: “*with E*” and “*without E*”. The performances of two models were then presented.

As a whole, a total of 531 datasets have a maximum value of sap flow below 10,000 (cm^3/h), accounting for about 86% of the total. Those with a maximum value of sap flow below 30,000 (cm^3/h) are even more than 600, about 98% of the total. Only one dataset has a maximum value of more than 50,000 (cm^3/h). The final threshold of the extreme value is set to 20,000(cm^3/h).

Figure 5 shows the NSE result in both groups. Overall, there is not much difference between these two models. The median NSE value of the *with E* model is 0.787, ranging from 0.656 to 0.866. After removing the extreme values, the median NSE value of the *without E* model instead drops by 0.035 to 0.753, and range from 0.678 to 0.801. The *with E* model is slightly better than the *without E* model, while the *without E* model has less variation.

Figure 4 The best NSE value and boxplot of the testing period for the experiment 2

Figure 5 The best NSE value and boxplot of the testing period for the experiment 3

5. Discussion

Sap flow was greatly influenced by meteorological factors. Previous studies have responded to that SW, AT, RH, VPD, PR and WS were the significant regulators of the measurement of sap flow (Chang et al., 2014; Han et al., 2019; Tian et al., 2017). In our results, the order of the importance of these variables was as follows: SW > VPD > RH > AT > WS > PR, which was almost consistent with the outcomes of Lei et al. (2010). It pointed to those factors with correlation coefficients greater than 0.4, including SW, VPD, RH and AT, referred to as moderate correlation (Schober et al., 2018), and we sought to find supporting arguments from the literature. Pataki and Oren (2003) claimed that solar radiation was the most important factor in describing the average stomatal behavior of deciduous forests, which led to the variations of sap flow. Lei et al. (2010) also explained that the rise in SW and AT in the morning led to a decline in RH, which increased of the water potential difference at leaf-to-air boundary. As a result, transpiration began and sap flow was initiated at the same time. Since VPD is composed of RH and AT, the three are supposed to interact with each other. To further explore, take *Pinus* as an example, we added temporal patterns of the four main environmental factors to the figure (as **Figure 6**). As previously estimated, the trends for SW and sap flow were significantly consistent, and the daily peaks of the two roughly matched. In contrast, the tendencies of the other three factors were similar to each another, but with lags compared to the peak of sap flow. When a single variable was used as the input feature instead of the original 6 environmental variables together, it was found that there was potential to obtain trends in sap flow, whether it was SW, VPD or even less relevant WS (as **Figure 7**). A possible explanation for this was that the correlation analysis and temporal pattern only indicated simple linear relationships and did not take into account the effect of nonlinear relationships and continuous time periods. LSTMs, on the other hand, took time series as input feature and found nonlinear relationships from them. In short, using LSTM, it allows us to use all environmental factors as input sources.

Figure 6 Daily sap flow and main environmental factors of *Pinus* (SW, AT, RH, VPD)

Figure 7 Simulation by different input feature of *Pinus* (SW, VPD, WS)

Missing data is a common problem in real world application that affects the quality of the development predictive models, as in neural networks as well. Missing data were briefly attributed to three categories (Houari *et al.*, 2014): (1) forgotten or lost values; (2) faulty equipment or incorrect measurements; (3) human error when processing data. Since our database came from the SAPFLUXNET, which have already accomplished data harmonization and quality control, we simply ignored the human error part and focused our attention on the first two conditions. The first type of missing data was forgotten or missing values, which in our data were blank values, marked as “NaN”. When encountering the sap flow data that has been lost for a long time, it was difficult to use the method of data supplementation. The most direct way was to omit these missing data, even though other features information was lost as well. For example, in our cases, the sap flow data of two stands had 10 full years of losing in total 90 years, and the rest of the lost data were in sporadic months. However, this type of missing data was not highly difficult in terms of data processing. It simply converted " NaN " values to zero values and eventually removed all the zeros, which were originally disregarded in the data processing. The second type of missing data was regarding incorrect measurements, also a more problematic issue. In this regard, the methodological aspects of sap flow must be first mentioned. Sap flow method was divided into four families (Flo *et al.*, 2019): (1) the dissipation family; (2) the pulse family; (3) the field family; (4) the balance family. Except the last one was to measure sap flow rate directly, the other three were to measure sap flux density. The practical problem with these sap flux density measurements was the variability of the radial patterns, which changed over time, and this caused further errors in thermal sapwood parameters (Vergeynst *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, long-term effects on sap flow method, such as wounding or signal attenuation (Peters *et al.*, 2018), could occur in either method case. Due to this reason, calibrating sap flow measurements were a critical procedure for obtaining accurate values, especially during long

periods of handling. In the SAPFLUXNET, however, most of the temporal data for sap flow have not undergone a species-specific calibration, and only 8% stands in our database have completed calibration, excluding these 2 stands used in this experiment. As an example, **Figure 8** demonstrates that the pattern of sap flow drops year by year, but at the same time, there is no obvious downward trend in all environmental variables. This was what mentioned in the second type of missing data, suggesting a possible bias in the sap flow measurement. On this point, there were approaches known as missing data model-based techniques that could be remediable (*García-Laencina et al., 2010*). Nevertheless, according to our result, the performance of the *no-pick* model was no worse than the *pick* model. This showed that our LSTM model had acceptable performance in the face of incorrect measurements and was more capable of diluting this misinformation when receiving a sufficiently large amount of data subsequently. Therefore, it had a confidence to train our datasets currently without any additional missing data model-based techniques.

Figure 8 The meteorological and sap flow data for plant 1 in FRA_HES_HE2_NON

In general, the majority of the RNN-based models merely utilized dynamic variables for input features (Tayal *et al.*, 2022). As shown in the warm-up, dynamic variables alone captured the rough pattern of sap flow. However, if the model is to be extended to a wider range of applications, static variables should be considered. Recently, some studies have only started to demonstrate that adding static variables to the LSTM model might improve the simulation (Kratzert *et al.*, 2019; Lin *et al.*, 2018; Tayal *et al.*, 2022). Basically, there were two approaches to combine both dynamic and static variable for a typical RNN architecture (Rahman *et al.*, 2020). The first approach used two independent neural networks to learn representations for time-series data and static characteristics, and then concatenates them in the final layer. In this way, static information only appeared at the last time step. The other approach, which also we used, was to directly take both types variables as input features to one recurrent neural model. This meant that the static variables were repeated at each time step. In the experiment 2, the *PL+ST* model was regarded as a benchmark for comparison. To begin with, the *PL* model and the *PL+ST* model were compared. The different between the two groups was whether site and stand variables were added. The results showed that the median NSE of the *PL* model was not only about 14% worse than that of the *PL+ST* model, but it also had a significantly larger amount of variance. A total of 14 site and stand variables provided more or less differentiated characteristics for the model. From the consequences, it was clear that this additional information, which was different from individual features, certainly offered a higher stability of the model simulations. On the other hand, as for the *ST* model and the *PL+ST* model, the difference between them was whether the plant variable, namely DBH, was taken in the input features. The performance gap between the two models became very apparent. The median NSE value of the *ST* model was about 84% worse than that of the *PL+ST* model, despite its low amount of variation. Honestly, this was clear to understand because stand and site variables shared the same information across several plants and did not provide individual characteristics to the model as did plant variables. Without the plant variable, the system would not be able to discern the difference between each plant and would fall into confusion. In other words, the plant variable was the key factor in forecasting sap flow for the extended scope of adoption of the LSTM model. Finally, the last comparison was between the *PL+ST* model and the *PL+ST extra* model. The plant variable of plant height was inserted in this extra model. The performance of the two models was nearly very close, with a gap of median NSE less than 2%, but a light improvement was still noted in the *PL+ST extra* model. For more details on plant variables, sap flow is in the xylem, so parameters related to sapwood, such as sapwood area or sapwood depth, are relatively important because they directly reflect the environment in which water is present. However, these variables were

not available or could not be estimated in more than half of plant data in the SAPFLUXNET (Poyatos *et al.*, 2021). Due to the lack of this information, alternatively, DBH was the main plant variable we used, which was complete in most plant-level metadata. Previous studies claimed a significant exponential relationship between DBH and sapwood area (Han *et al.*, 2019), and again, due to this absence, we could only examined the correlation between DBH and sap flow, but also found that such a possible exponential relationship exist among them (as **Figure 9.a**). To confirm that the plant variables would refine the model, plant height was deemed to be the next variable addition, although due to its absence it still could not appear in the next stage. Its exponential relationship with sap flow was also tested and found to be less pronounced than for DBH (as **Figure 9.b**), but it was still optimized as far as overall model performance is concerned. Though, there has not been much experimental evidence, it is estimated from the properties of neural networks that adding more plant variables, whether they have high or low correlation with sap flow, would enhance the strength of the LSTM model.

Figure 9 Exponential correlations between maximal sap flow and DBH or height

First of all, it needs to clarify the identification between extreme values and outliers. Outliers with valid data points are also known as extreme values, while invalid outliers indicate data containing some sort of error (Suboh and Aziz, 2020). In this case, we focused only on the former. Statistically, the maximum sap flow that exceeded about 14,000 (cm^3/h) in all our datasets was considered an extreme value. However, as a conservative estimate, the threshold for the extreme value was raised and set at 20,000 (cm^3/h). A total of 24 datasets in our database had extreme values, representing about 4% of the overall. Among them, only one stand had a maximum sap flow above 50,000 (cm^3/h), occurring in the “PRT_LEZ_ARN”, while it had four plant data with maximum sap flow values all above the extreme threshold. However, a review of the variables in this plant data revealed that it did not have extremely high or low input features, and as an example, the plant had 98.36 (m) at DBH, not the widest

diameter of all. This did not provide a basis for the model to illustrate why this maximum sap flow appeared. Due to such data conditions, when taking a closer look at our results, it was found that the simulated values would have upper limits in either the training data or the test data, depending on which side the maximum sap flow data was assigned. Two examples are shown in **Figure 10**. While the model still performed satisfactory, the pattern of observed and predicted data throughout was slightly unexpected. The cause of this phenomenon was possibly thought to be the neuronal network saturation, referring to a state in which the main output of the neuron approaches the asymptotic end value of the bounded activation function, leading to a destruction of the model learning ability (*Rakitienskaia and Engelbrecht, 2015*). To detect whether the saturation of the neuronal network could be improved, we did an additional experiment by randomly selecting 300 plant data, including the maximum sap flow data, as the training data. There were two approaches, the first one was to increase the number of epoch and the other one was to add nodes of the hidden layer, shown as **Figure 11**. The consequences revealed that both methods slowed down the occurrence of neuronal network saturation, especially the second one, but still did not prevent it completely and required further consideration of overfitting problems and extra computation time. Back to the discussion of two models in this experiment, Boulmaiz et al. (2020) claims that LSTM models might have some difficulties when facing extreme events in the learning data, therefore it was recommended to ignore data periods with extreme events. However, in our results, removing the extremes did not directly improve the model, and the sap flow predictions were still significantly underestimated at low flows. Another aspect was that, in reality, it is possible to encounter trees that produce significantly large sap flows, so that the occurrence of extreme values should not be easily ignored if the LSTM model is to be more tolerable.

Figure 10 Examples of the phenomenon of neuronal network saturation

(a) increase the number of epochs (5, 10, 50)

(b) add nodes of the hidden layer (128, 256, 512)

Figure 11 The NSE value of the training period by changing hyperparameters

6. Conclusion

In this thesis, we applied open data to attempt an unprecedented model of sap flow prediction across European spatial scales. Given the performance results of the model, this certainly had the potential to be developed and made operational for subsequent relevant studies.

In terms of environmental factors, through correlation analysis and daily patterns, we found that SW was the most important factor. It had the highest correlation with sap flow and daily stream flows of both were remarkably similar. However, when starting LSTMs simulation with a single element as the input feature, it was observed that most elements could capture the general trend of the sap flow, regardless of their strong or weak correlation with the sap flow. This was the benefit of neural networks for their flexibility in dealing with nonlinear shapes and their ability to estimate unknown functions. Meanwhile, neural networks were capable of accommodating numerous dynamic variables. If other well established data, such as soil moisture coefficients, are collected in the future, the LSTM model will have more information for advancement.

Missing data had an impact on follow up data processing and training. In our case, the missing values were well dealt with by directly omitting them, but the incorrect measurements were relatively complicated. The main reason was that long-term effects on sap flow method were not adjusted easily, which was why conducting species-specific calibrations was needed.

Although we demonstrated that the missing data did not actually interfere much with the LSTM model, it was argued that the reliability of the using data would increase if a higher percentage of calibrated time series data existed.

The static variables played a very important role in the input features of the LSTM model, given that the model was required to extend to a larger range of scales. After comparing the presence or absence of various static variables, it was evident that plant variables representing individual trees would allow the model to work better. Site and stand variables were easier to obtain that could make the model robust despite being shared by several plants. At this stage, our analysis of plant variables focused only on DBH and plant height, which were relatively easy to measure, and it is suggested that more plant variables can be explored in subsequent studies.

As for the extreme values, from our point of view, it was unhelpful and impractical to neglect these values in the sap flow data. The performance of the model was not better by ignoring the extreme period, and on the other hand, higher sap flow could actually occur. However, a solution was still being sought for the neural network phenomenon of saturation due to extreme values. Although not completely solved, we proposed that increasing the number of epochs and adding hidden layers of nodes might help to slow down the phenomenon. This issue should be explored in greater depth afterwards.

Regarding the future outlook of this thesis, three main points are suggested. Firstly, it is about the strategy of data selection. To optimize the amount of our datasets and available variables, static variables that exceed the assigned absence number were excluded. However, without investigating the association of these variables with sap flow, some important variables might not be selected, such as sapwood area. Therefore, the selection system is supposed to be developed in the future. Secondly, our models have not been tuned with much hyperparameters. Since we assumed our task as a pioneering study, the main emphasis was on feasibility. However, such adjustments are necessary if the model wants to be more reliable, and now that the amount of data is already enormous, this is becoming a truly time-consuming task. To end up, although the data were taken from the European region, it was more precisely based on five tree genera. The genus name was a special feature belonging to a plant variable, but in fact its function should be closer to that of classification. That is, theoretically, our model should then be tested for applicability to the same genera outside of the European region in order to explicitly define its range of suitability.

Thanks to the advent of the SAPFLUXNET, the first temporal patterns of sap flow data with a global perspective, we have successfully constructed a European database and used it to train LSTM models for forecasting sap flow. With continued growth of sap flow data in the future,

we anticipate that this thesis will serve as a pioneer for those subsequent studies that attempt to make sap flow predictions by using machine learning and open data on a regional or global scale.

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